

THE ESSENCE AND FEATURES OF POLITICAL PROCESSES IN POLITICAL SCIENCE

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Uzbekistan has been striving for progress for more than 30 years, moving forward towards the welfare of society, economic growth. For history, this is a small opportunity, however, the picture of the rapid development of the side environment, the expansion of globalization is a time-lapse, and society requires political power to determine the directions of rapid and effective development. However, the notion of progress would have been for power only when there was a development, a great departure from the steps and an advance, an opportunity to see results in this easy and fast opportunity. However, the development in the geography of Maracasian Asia means that it is carried out first of all through rational cooperation with various large political forces, political poles, ensuring the security of the territory and society, and tolerance to various political and seasonal threats. In this regard, Uzbekistan after 2016, taking into account the global political order, The Shape of the criteria for International Development, Strategies for a certain period are being developed based on our national and foreign characteristics. These programs, which embody various aspects of development, clearly show the plans of the state for the next five years. This is done on the basis of consultation with the people.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about this in detail in his book "strategy of New Uzbekistan". In which the sentence is called:

"At the present time, our people live with such ambitious goals as achieving the standard of living characteristic of the most developed countries, building a new society. The creation of a modern and attractive image of our country, the establishment of a new Uzbekistan has become the main goal of our compatriots.

In turn, the systematic and effective organization of productive activity on the achievement of this goal, the achievement of the effectiveness of our work determine the essence and priorities of our reforms.

On January 28, 2022, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree "on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 .

This strategy reflects the national and historical characteristics of the people, modern requirements and needs, and the National idea and ideology in the essence of this expresses the content of future political processes.

In order to interpret and interpret dynamic changes in the political life of society, to study, the concept of "political process" is used in political science. The political process also characterizes political practice as a universal category of political science. It reflects the variability of politics and reveals the interaction of political institutions and political entities that perform certain functions and "roles". The political process can also be interpreted as the

general activity of all subjects of political relations associated with the formation, development, transformation and functioning of the political system, mediating state power. In the general social context, the nature of the state is the Office of economic life, while society forms socio-political life. The most important elements inherent in its structure – the subjects and objects of politics, the specific means and angles of political activity – indicate the direction and methods of implementing political practice. To analyze political processes, modern political science uses a number of methodological approaches; but the following paradigms are most effective for assessing their dynamics.

In the Professional literature there are several basic approaches to the study of the essence and content of the political process.

Supporters of the institutional approach in the first place consider political phenomena associated with the change of political institutions as the main subjects of political processes. In this case, social infrastructure is taken into account, either partially or indirectly, since it has secondary importance.

Secondly, representatives of the behavioral approach consider individual individuals or groups of people to be subjects of politics. Therefore, in this case, the political process is perceived as the result of the behavior, political will and interests of these subjects. However, in this definition, political processes are broader and not fully reflected structurally. Thus, the units of chronological measurement are also small. They make it possible to study politics only within the framework of everyday life.

Thirdly, the structural-functional approach emphasizes the importance of the internal structural and functional elements of the political system in the context of the political process. In this case, as units of analysis, not individuals and groups are considered, but the central institutions of the political system (and the entire system itself), as well as their functional structure.

The main emphasis is on the micro-level and macro-level of the political process, which is characterized as the integrity of the political system. D.Easton noted that the goal of political processes is "to make an acceptable decision for groups of leading interests."

Political processes also differ in their nature and typology. In this regard, political processes differ in their size, actions, factors, interaction between them and other signs.

A.Referring to the typology of political processes, Soloviev notes that political processes for society can be divided into basic and peripheral types. The main processes lie in a change in the systemic characteristics of political life (for example, the formation of a state institution by the government). As for peripheral processes, they are based on less significant changes that, in principle, cannot seriously affect the dominant objects of power. The author also separately defines such types of the political process as closed and open, stable and transitional .

A closed political process is a change that can be assessed as a monovalent within the framework of good/bad, acceptable / unacceptable criteria.

An open political process is a change that allows you to predict how positively or negatively the subject will be affected, as well as what strategy to choose for the future. In other words, such processes characterize changes that occur in the most incomprehensible political situations. Sustainable political processes imply a stable repetition of political relations.

Modern political science discursively recognizes the significant variety and dynamics of political processes and confirms this with their typologies. Thus, according to the criterion of

the scale of the policy that political processes carry out by them, the following are distinguished:

- the macrodarage of political processes is manifested at the stages of the functioning of political institutions: for example, the state, regime, parties (historical, evolutionary, revolutionary process). Therefore, they are defined as a cycle of political shifts, successive changes in the state of the political system. They are characterized by the participation of "large" participants - political elites, classes, institutions of power, and can be measured only in large units of time (the formation/disintegration of the Empire, the era of modernization, democratic transition).

- processes at the micro-level-can be direct political events, for example, "some kind of resultant sum of their tasks characteristic of various socio-political entities." These are everyday processes in politics that occur between "small" participants and are associated with the direct interaction of individual, group or corporate interests (political interaction in Parliament, structures of local government).

In addition, transitional processes represent a lack of basic characteristics and factors in the organization of power, which occurs precisely in the conditions of unbalanced political activity of the main subjects.

In this context, it is necessary to refer to the theory of political processes, which gives a more complete picture of behavior and procedural phenomena in politics.

The mobilization of Social Action, known as the theory of political processes, is significant in that it serves to form political possibilities, mobilization structures and processes. This theory, developed in the United States in the 1970s and 1980s and based on the analysis of the struggle for Civil Rights, focuses on the interaction between such attributes of movement as organizational structure, economic and political context. Critics argue that this theory is overly structural and immutable. Recent research by key theorists in the theory of political processes has focused on a more dynamic analysis of the repetitive mechanisms and processes of politics. The theory of political processes is a logical conclusion of criticism against the then social scientific views. Because scientists have also put forward the scientific view that demonstrators and other participants in the social movement are "irrational gangs", in which the collective mentality begins to act. In fact, these actions were not caused by alienation or abnormal psychological inclinations, but were intended, on the contrary, to achieve political goals and state legal grievances, to find solutions to them, to solve the problem. In establishing this new analysis, the three precursors that made a specific contribution to the theory of political processes deserve attention.

First, M. Olson's (1965) collection behavior analysis changed the old notions of demonstrators' irrationality, examining the rational choices people made before joining the movement.

Secondly, in an impressive analysis of the movement of farm workers, J. McCarthy and M. Zald found that the availability of resources to the movement, in contrast to the level of oppression, explains the basis of changes in the level of mobilization. This prospect of resource mobilization not only takes into account material goods as resources, but also aspects such as organizational strength and the presence of elite allies.

Third, F. Piven and R. Cloward (1978) focused on important aspects of the economic and political system. Only in periods of great crisis on the scale of the entire system, for example, in times of depression, actions were able to receive benefits from the elite.

The combination of the three approaches mentioned above forms the basis of the theory of political processes. One of his main works on these processes is C. In Tilly's book mobilization for revolution, the author synthesizes these three approaches with other political views. C. Tilly (1978) notes that the interaction of the three (interests, organization and opportunity) structural elements explains in a sense the degree of mobilization and collective action as well as how important it is. In this place, interests represent the potential results of participation in political processes. And opportunity also indicates the size of political power, the likelihood of pressure and the weakness of the goal. Its activity has an indirect effect on social movement.

So no matter how similar and consistent aspects political processes have, these processes also differ from each other in their specific features. In addition, the study of any political process requires a specific approach or the application of a combination of certain approaches.

At this point, only a speech approach can be considered relatively universal effective, since all political processes, regardless of the type of political regime or other political factors, have their own speech, reflecting the peculiarities of the political process, thanks to the model of political culture prevailing in this society.

References:

1. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Янги Ўзбекистон стратегияси. – “O‘zbekiston” нашриёти, 2021. 7 бет.
2. Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 29.01.2022 й., 06/22/60/0082-сон, 18.03.2022 й., 06/22/89/0227-сон
3. Соловьёв А. И. Политология: Политическая теория, политические технологии. - М.: Аспект Пресс, 2006. - 559 б.
4. Дегтярев А.А. Основы политической теории. – М., 1998, с 147.
5. McCarthy, J., & Zald, M. (1977). Resource Mobilisation and Social Movements: A Partial Theory. *American Journal of Sociology*, 82, pp.1212-1241-бетлар.
6. Alimbetova.G.A. (2022). THE ESSENCE OF THE CONTENT OF POLITICAL IDEOLOGY. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 2(12), 102–106.
7. Alimbetova .G, Socio - Ethical Problems of Development National Idea
8. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices* 1 (1), 33-39, 2021
9. Alimbetova .G, *ISSRA Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Studies*
10. *ISSRA. Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Studies* 1 (1), 1-4, 2021
11. Алимбетова Г.А. Сиёсий жараёнларда мафқурани тадқиқ этишнинг назарий методолик асослари Бердақ атындағы Қарақалпақ Мәмлекетлик Университетиниң Хабарщысы 2(1) , 177-179, 2022
12. Алимбетова Г.А. Сиёсий ғоя ва мафқуранинг сиёсий жараёнларга таъсири Бердақ атындағы Қарақалпақ Мәмлекетлик Университетиниң Хабарщысы 3(1), 137-140, 2022
13. А Байрыева. Исеним тәрбиясы. Вестник каракалпакского государственного университета имени Бердаха 15 (1-2 ...101 2012
14. BA Kurbanovna. Trends in parliamentary effectiveness in ensuring the development of society. *Восточно-европейский научный журнал*, 33-36 15. 2020
15. BA Kurbanovna. Essence, Development And Role Of Representative Authority In The Development Of Society. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching* 2, 113-117 14 2021

- 16.A Bayrieva. Ensuring Balance Among Branches of Public Power During the Development of Civil Society in Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine* 7 (2), 2233-2239 8 2020
- 17.АК Байрыева. Ўзбекистонда вакиллик ҳокимияти органлари ва фуқаролик жамияти институтлари ҳамкорлигининг сиёсий-ҳуқуқий масалалари. *Международный журнал консенсус* 1 (3) 8 2020
- 18.АК Байрыева. Национальные духовные ценности и духовное воспитание. *Научная мысль*, 39-43 2 2015
- 19.АВ Qurbanovna. Political and legal issues of cooperation between representative authorities and institutions of civil society in Uzbekistan.
- 20.ЭХ Эгамбердиев, Ф Кутлымуратов. Расторжение брака в органах загс при взаимном согласии супругов. *Хабаршысы* 4, 103 4 2019
- 21.FK Kalbaevich. Legal Entities–As Subjects of Civil Law. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities* 8, 57-59. 2022
- 22.U Nadirbekova, R Bayjanova, F Kutlimuratov. issues of formation of legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, Which will radically improve the activities of the legal service. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research* 2 (6), 471-474. 2022
- 23.ФК Кутлымуратов. Қайта ташкил этишнинг алоҳида шаклларида фуқаролик-ҳуқуқий мажбуриятларининг ўзгариши. *журнал правовых исследований* 7 (1). 2022
- 24.KF Kalbaevich. Creditor's approval for "transferring debt" and problems of its processing. *Thematics Journal of Law* 5 (9) . 2021
- 25.KF Kalbaevich. Protection of creditors'rights-as a civil law sub institution while reorganizing commercial legal entities. *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities* 1 (1.4 Legal. 2021
- 26.K F.K. The experience of foreign countries in protecting the rights of creditors during the reorganization of legal entities. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan* 17 (2), 91-94 . 2021
- 27.Ф Қутлымуратов. Юридик шахсни қайта ташкил этишни ҳақиқий эмас деб топиш одил судлов, 14-16 .2021
- 28.Ф Қутлымуратов. Қайта ташкил этилаётган юридик шахс каредиторлари ҳуқуқларининг кафолатлари. *Жамият ва бошқарув* 93 (3), 31-37. 2021
- 29.АО Жуманов, Ф Цутлымуратов. Фуқароларнинг марказлашган тартибда маиший ва ичимлик сувдан фойдаланишида дуцций масалаларнинг тадлили. *хабаршысы*, 129. 2017
- 30.JI Baxytovna. Science in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. *Results of National Scientific Research* 1 (1), 74-81
- 31.ZI Bakhytovna. Foreign cooperation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the field of environmental protection. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 3, 58-60
- 32.I Jollybekova. Wissenschaft der Republik Karakalpakstan. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology* 2 (12), 171-174. 2022
- 33.I Jollybekova. Videnskab i republikken Karakalpakstan. *Академические исследования в современной науке* 1 (19), 265-269. 2022
- 34.I Jolibekova. Development of foreign cultural cooperation of the republic of Karakalpakstan. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology* 2 (12), 107-111. 2022

35. JI Bakhitovna. Entwicklung der ausländischen kulturellen Zusammenarbeit der Republik Karakalpakstan. Models and methods for increasing the efficiency of innovative research 2. 2022
36. ИБ Жоллыбекова. Мустақиллик йилларида Қорақалпоғистон Республикасининг илм соҳасида ва кадрлар тайёрлашда ҳорижий ҳамкорлиги. Лучший инноватор в области науки 1 (1), 782-789 2022
37. ИБ Жоллыбекова. Вопросы оценки образования в современных условиях. Материалы международной научно-практической конференции 1 (2), 69-71 2017
38. ИБ Жоллыбекова. International relations in the field of science. Technology and education of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Postępy w nauce w ostatnich latach. Nowych rozwiązani. Сборник научных трудов. 2013
39. ИБ Жоллыбекова. Основы международных экономических отношений в законодательстве Каракалпакстана. Вестник Национального Государственного Университета имени Мирзо Улугбек 1 (1 ... 2011)
40. JI Bahytovna. International relations in the field of science, technology and education of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Достижения науки за последние годы. Новые наработки. 2015.

